

Design, Fabrication and Testing of Chewing Gum-Based Electronic Components and Sensors

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Abstract—Modern trends in many industrial sectors and shortage and high prices of classical electronic components has imposed the necessity for creating electronic components from the materials which we used every day. Such a type of material is a chewing gum. This paper presents the process of design, manufacturing and testing of the resistor, capacitor and inductor from a commercial chewing gum as it is bought. Electrical parameters were measured using an Impedance analyzer in the frequency range from 100 Hz to 40 MHz. Moreover, from recycled and reused chewing gum as a substrate, we fabricated antenna using aluminum foil as a conductive layer. The force sensor was also created based on capacitive principle where dielectric layer was reused chewing gum and gold and aluminum layer were used as conductors. The results presented in this paper contribute to the creation of an alternative kit for chewing gum-based electronics with potential applications in oral cavity and biomedicine.

Keywords—chewing gum, resistor, inductor, capacitor, antenna, force sensor.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the progress of the global economy, and the fast development of modern science and technology, a great assortment of electronic devices has been widely used in human society, playing an important role in many fields of our life particularly in healthcare sector. Moving towards a more circular economy is essential to create and test new types of materials in electronics. This will push the development of the concept of Green Electronics [1], which means that materials which we used comes from sustainable sources, and that they do not impact the environment at its end of life. The progress in this emerging field of Electronics may benefit from development of bioresorbable and edible electronic materials derived from nature [2] or food-based materials [3] as substrates in flexible or wearable electronics.

Such a type of material, which is low-cost and even reusable is a chewing gum and can be applied in original form or in recycled form. A chewing gum can have important roles in our daily life such as cleaning the mouth, promoting facial blood circulation, etc. A recent study [4] investigated the feasibility of using chewing gum as a substrate for the fabrication of flexible and stretchable electrodes. The results showed that the electrical conductivity and mechanical properties of the chewing gum were suitable for the development of wearable devices. Another study [5] demonstrated the use of chewing gum as a matrix for encapsulating and delivering therapeutic drugs. These findings highlight the potential of edible materials like chewing gum in the development of safe and biocompatible wearable electronics and drug delivery systems. In [6] authors presented sensor manufactured from a discarded chewed gum and an edible salt solution and the sensor was applied in

detecting various human motions and in personal healthcare monitoring. Combination of a chewing gum and MWCNTs was used in [7] to construct high performance strain applied as bodily motion sensors as well as to monitor humidity changes. Moreover, in [8] authors prepared a chewing gum gel with polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) having good mechanical and self-healing properties and utilized to monitor different types of human motion or temperature. Additionally, a chewing gum with Ag nanoparticles suspension for detection of malachite green in live fish skin was reported in [9]. As can be concluded from the presented open literature review, usual application of chewing gums was in sensors application, but there is a gap in creation of other chewing gum-based electronic components such as resistors, capacitors or inductors, for instance.

The integration of edible materials like chewing gum in the development of wearable electronics is a relatively new field of research with great potential. Chewing gum, in particular, has shown promise as a substrate for the fabrication of flexible and stretchable electrodes [4]. However, there are still several challenges that should be solved in order to make the integration of chewing gum in wearable electronics more feasible and practical. One of the biggest challenges is the variability in the properties of chewing gum, as it can vary based on the brand, formulation, and storage conditions [5]. This can make it difficult to achieve consistent and reproducible results in the development of wearable devices. Another challenge is the development of processing techniques that can be used to incorporate other functional materials, such as sensors and therapeutic drugs, into the chewing gum matrix [7]. Despite these challenges, there are also several possibilities for the integration of chewing gum in wearable electronics. For example, the usage of chewing gum as a matrix for encapsulating and delivering therapeutic drugs [5] has the potential to revolutionize the field of drug delivery. Additionally, the ability to create flexible and stretchable electrodes using chewing gum [4] could lead to the development of wearable devices that are more comfortable to wear and less prone to breaking [10]. In conclusion, the integration of materials like chewing gum in the development of edible, wearable electronics is a rapidly evolving field with many challenges, limitations, and possibilities. With continued research and development, it is possible to overcome these challenges and realize the full potential of these materials in the creation of safe, biocompatible, and functional wearable devices.

Here, we present the fundamental electronic components, namely resistor, interdigitated capacitor, inductor, antenna, as well as sensors manufactured using chewing gum as a substrate and edible gold, silver, or aluminum as conductive materials. Electro-Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) was used for measurement of electrical parameters of the manufactured electronic components.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Materials

Two types of sugar free chewing gums Orbit (Mondelēz International East Hanover, New Jersey, United States) and Juicy Fruit (Mondelēz International East Hanover, New Jersey, United States) were purchased in the local store (Figure 1(a)). After the purchasing, the chewing gums have been used immediately in this study, avoiding the humidity or heat have influence on the samples. In this study these two chewing gums were used as substrates bearing in mind their flat surface, with total dimensions 19 mm × 53 mm and with thickness around 1 mm. Three types of materials were applied on these substrates as conductive layer, namely, edible gold or edible silver in the form of leaves (thin sheet) or aluminum foil, as can be seen in Figures 1(b)-1(d). The thicknesses of the conductive layers were as follows: gold layer - 3 μm, silver layer - 2.2 μm and aluminum foil - 9 μm. When it was necessary to provide a good adhesion of conductive layer on a chewing gum substrate, the honey was used.

Fig. 1. (a) Two types of chewing gums used as a substrate, and applied conductive materials (b) gold, (c) silver, (d) aluminum foil.

B. Manufactured electronic components

First, we manufactured electrical resistor based on chewing gum as a substrate and at the top melted sugar in the caramel form was deposited. In order to create some kind of surface mounted component, aluminum foil was applied for terminals. Fabricated component is depicted in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Resistor created on a chewing gum.

After that, interdigitated capacitor structures were manufactured on a chewing gum, as can be seen in Figure 3. The width of the conductive segments (fingers) was 4 mm,

and the length of fingers was equal to 12 mm, whereas the spacing between the fingers was approximately 2 mm.

Fig. 3. Interdigitated capacitor manufactured on chewing gum with conductive electrodes created from (a) silver, (b) gold, and (c) aluminum.

Next, we created inductors on a chewing gum in a zig-zag pattern as it is shown in Figure 4. The width of conductive segments was 4 mm.

Fig. 4. Zig-zag inductors manufactured on chewing gum with conductive electrodes created from (a) gold, (b) silver, and (c) aluminum.

As a next step in our study, we fabricated a Z-shaped antenna, with the same design and dimensions as we already published, but on textile substrate [11], using aluminum foil on reused chewing gum. The chewing gum was chewed for 15 minutes, sterilized and flattened by roller in order to get 1 mm thick substrate. The manufactured antenna is presented in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Z-shaped antenna from aluminum manufactured on reused chewing gum of Juicy Fruit.

In the final step of our study in order to investigate sensor applications of a reused chewing gum, a pressure sensor was manufactured based on the plate capacitive principle where the dielectric material in the middle was a recycled chewing

gum (with a thickness of 5 mm) and the top and bottom electrodes were fabricated from gold, silver and aluminum (dimensions 1.8 cm $\times$ 2.5 cm) as can be seen in Figure 6. Bearing in mind that reused chewing gum has sticky properties itself, in this and previous case (antenna) it was not necessary to use honey.

Fig. 6. Capacitive pressure sensor manufactured from a chewing gum in the middle and conductive electrodes, on top and bottom, from (a) silver, (b) gold, and (c) aluminum.

C. Instruments

For measuring electrical parameters such as resistance, capacitance, or inductance as a function of frequency (in the range from 100 Hz to 40 MHz), Impedance/Gain – Phase Analyzer HP 4194A was used (Figure 7). A vector network analyzer was used for measuring S11 parameter of the antenna. For testing the developed pressure sensors on chewing gum, the tension test instrument Instron 34SC – 2 kN was applied along with U1733C LCR Meter for recording measured capacitance (Figure 8).

Fig. 7. Experimental set-up for measuring electrical parameters.

Fig. 8. Experimental set-up for testing pressure sensors.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section results are presented for the following manufactured electronic components: (a) resistor, (b) interdigitated capacitor, (c) zig-zag inductor, (d) antenna, and (e) pressure sensor.

A. Measured results for resistor

First, the electrical resistance was measured as a function of frequency and results for two types of chewing gums are depicted in Figure 9.

Fig. 9. Electrical resistance as a function of frequency for two types of chewing gums.

As can be seen from Figure 9 the results demonstrated the same decreasing trend of resistance as frequency increases. The range of resistance was from 10⁷ up to 10³ Ω. For similar length of resistor (around 5 cm) as in our study, authors on [3], reported the value 2 kΩ of edible resistor created from sweet potato starch and carbonized cotton candy. In order to demonstrate sensors application of this type of the resistive sensor in oral cavity, we exposed the sensor to different fluids and this is presented in Figure 10. Point (1) means dry sensor, (2) is under the influence of artificial saliva consisting of carboxymethyl cellulose and made in accordance with a recipe developed by the Pharmacy Institution of Belgrade (registered under the master preparations of the Republic of Serbia), (3) artificial saliva + Listerine (Johnson & Johnson, New Brunswick, NJ,) and (4) artificial saliva + Listerine + Curaprox (Curaden AG, Zürich, Switzerland), in equal ratio. It can be concluded from Figure 10 that electrical resistance was decreased with adding different fluids, due to increasing the conductivity between terminals when the liquid solution is applied comparing to the caramelized sugar at the top of the structure. The proposed resistive sensor structure can be used in oral cavity to detect the type of the fluid. The effect of simultaneous use of chewing gum and mouthwash can vary depending on the type of gum and mouthwash being used. It is clinically suggested that using sugar-free chewing gum after using a mouthwash can help to increase the amount of saliva in the mouth, which can help to neutralize harmful acids and reduce the risk of caries. However, it is also important to note that some mouthwashes contain alcohol or other ingredients that can cause a drying effect in the mouth, which can counteract the benefits of using chewing gum [12], [13].

Fig. 10. Resistance when the component from Fig. 2, was exposed to different type of fluids at the frequency point of 100 Hz.

B. Measured results for capacitor

Figure 11(a)-11(c) presents the results for measured capacitance as a function of frequency for two types of analyzed chewing gums and three different types of conductors.

Fig. 11. Capacitance as a function of frequency, for two types of chewing gums and for (a) silver, (b) gold and (c) aluminum.

At the lower frequency regime, a sharp decrease in capacitance can be noticed with an increase in frequency. At frequencies higher than 100 kHz, however, there was a plateau in capacitance, where the values in the range from 1 to 10 pF were obtained. The capacitance graph is almost the same for two types of conductive electrodes created from Ag and Al and only for Au we noticed some difference which can be

attributed to non-uniform linkage gold electrodes for these types of substrates. This behavior however, can be the claim of the suitability of edible materials, as the edible silver has a similar behavior across the examined frequency spectrum with the aluminum foil, albeit at a different capacitance, which can always be tuned by tuning the dielectric or geometry.

C. Measured results for inductors

Figure 12(a) shows measured results for aluminum zig-zag inductor on two types of chewing gums, whereas Figure 12(b) depicts graphs for silver and Orbit chewing gum. Other combinations were fragile, preventing us to get reliable measurement results.

Fig. 12. Inductance as a function of frequency, for (a) two types of chewing gums and aluminum as a conductor and (b) Orbit chewing gum as a substrate and silver as a materials for conductive segments of zig-zag structure.

It can be noticed that the values of inductance that can be achieved were around 370 nH and relatively stable in the frequency range from 1 kHz to 1 MHz.

D. Measured results for antenna

We measured S11 parameter as a function of frequency, for antenna shown in Figure 5 and results are presented in Figure 13. First the measurement was performed on antenna in dry conditions and after that when the antenna was exposed to the influence of some liquids, for example Ice tea (Lipton Ice Tea PepsiCo, Inc. Purchase, New York, United States) and Pepsi Cola (PepsiCo, Inc. Purchase, New York, United States). Lipton Ice Tea and Pepsi Cola are both carbonated, non-alcoholic beverages that are widely consumed globally. However, they differ in terms of their ingredients, taste, and nutritional value. Lipton Ice Tea is made from tea leaves, water, sugar, and natural flavorings, while Pepsi Cola is made from carbonated water, high fructose corn syrup, caramel color, and a blend of natural and artificial flavors. Lipton Ice Tea has a slightly acidic pH of around 4.5, while Pepsi Cola

has a pH of around 2.5 to 3.0, which makes it more acidic. Lipton Ice Tea is usually less viscous than Pepsi Cola, with a lower sugar content. The simultaneous use of chewing gum and Ice tea or Pepsi Cola has not been widely studied and there is limited research available on the topic. However, some studies have demonstrated that chewing gum can affect the taste perception of foods and beverages, including Ice tea and Pepsi Cola. For example, chewing gum can temporarily alter the sense of taste and cause a reduction in sweetness perception. The impact of chewing gum on the pH, viscosity, and sugar content of Ice tea and Pepsi Cola is not well established and requires further research. The potential impact of simultaneous use of chewing gum and soft drinks on oral health and dental hygiene should also be considered [14], [15].

Fig. 13. Amplitude of S11 parameter as a function of frequency for antenna on reused chewing gum, also exposed to different fluids.

It can be concluded that for dry antenna amplitude of S11 parameter was 21.26 dB at the frequency around 1.392 GHz. The amplitude was changed having a value of 18.72 dB at 1.282 GHz and 17.09 dB on 1.372 GHz for the same antenna when it exposed to Ice tea and Pepsi, respectively. In this study, our idea was not to target a specific frequency range, but to demonstrate proof of concept of realization of antenna on chewing gum. However, the obtained range this range corresponds to L-Band (1 ÷ 2 GHz) and is used for SatNav and Mobile Communications. It is interesting to mention that the same frequency point around 1.35 GHz was reported by measurement also in [16], for Z-shaped antenna manufactured on glossy paper using silver ink, with amplitude of return loss around 19 dB.

E. Measured results for force sensor

Finally, we manufactured force sensors based on the capacitive principle, where reused Orbit chewing gum was used in the middle, whereas the top and bottom layer were from aluminum, silver and gold. Using the tension test instrument, force was applied on this structure and capacitance was measured with LCR meter at set intervals. Capacitance as a function of applied force can be seen in Figure 14(a) for gold electrodes and in Figure 14(b) for aluminum electrodes.

Based on the formula (1) for capacitance of the plate capacitor

$$C = \epsilon_r * \epsilon_o * \frac{S}{d} \quad (1)$$

when the force is higher, the distance (d) between the electrodes is lower, which means the capacitance will increase and this behavior can be noticed in Figure 14. We obtained

very good linear approximation with goodness of fit, $R^2 = 0.921$ for gold electrodes, and 0.954 for aluminum electrodes. It is also illustrated in inset of Figure 14 how the force sensor looks like at the beginning of experiment and at the end. It can be noticed that gold electrodes were degraded and aluminum foil was very stable, but chewing gum changed the shape under the influence of force, according to the expectations.

Fig. 14. Capacitance as a function of applied force for chewing gum in the middle and (a) gold, and (b) aluminum, as conductive layers.

We can conclude that proposed chewing gum force or pressure sensors can be used up to forces around 30 N, which corresponds to the bite force of children [17], [18]. These findings are in line with previous reports that suggest that chewing gum has potential for use as a substrate in the development of edible bite force sensors [19], [7]. However, further research is needed to optimize the materials and design of the sensors for practical applications.

IV. CONCLUSION

For further fast growth of the green electronics field, it is significant to create a new set of electronic components which are manufactured based on foodstuff or even recycled materials. The main findings of this paper can be summarized as follows:

- (1) From commercial flat chewing gums and conductive segments of aluminum, gold, or silver, we fabricated (a) a resistor and the range from $k\Omega$ to $M\Omega$ was achieved, (b) interdigitated capacitor with capacitance in the range from dozens of pF up to 100 pF and (c) zig-zag inductor with inductance around 370 nH.
- (2) On recycled chewing gums we fabricated (a) Z-shaped antenna for operation in GHz range and (b) force sensors with maximum applied force up to 30 N.

The presented results contribute to moving the field of unconventional electronics towards more realistic application, following the zero waste concept.

In future work, it may be useful to study some of the presented components as sensors for *in-vivo* oral cavity applications.

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